

A simple volumetric method of mancozeb residues analysis in edible plants

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Mancozeb residues, micronutrients (Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) in plants have been determined using complexometric titration. Disodium salt of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, eriochrome black T and ammonia buffer of pH 10 have been used as titrant, indicator and medium respectively. The results of volumetry have been compared with those obtained by atomic absorption spectrophotometry.

Mancozeb¹⁻³ is an important fungicide extensively used both as foliar spray as well as soil drench for the control of various plant diseases in winter crops in Aligarh (U.P.). Therefore in continuation to our previous work⁴, the complexometric titration has been extended to determine mancozeb metallic residues in edible plants. The results obtained are discussed.

Results and discussion

Mancozeb (10 ml of 5% aqueous suspension) was sprayed on wet samples of meithi (*Trigonella fornum graecum*) (230 g); spinach (*Spinacia oleracea*) (220 g); sarson (*Brassica sp*) (250 g); chukander leaves (*Beta vulgaris*) (180 g) and chukander root (272 g). However, 5 ml of 5% mancozeb aqueous suspension was sprayed on radish leaves (*Raphanus sativus*) (270 g). These samples were dried till their weights were constant which are given in the parentheses : Meithi (11.5 g), spinach (14.3 g), radish leaves (17.3 g), sarson (11.2 g), chukander leaves (11.4 g) and chukander root (13.4 g). After that the samples (0.5 g each) were analyzed for Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} using EDTA titration. The results obtained in $\mu g g^{-1}$ of dried sample are given in column 1 of Table 1.

In second set of experiment the powdered, dried sample (0.5 g) was dosed with 1–4 ml of 0.271% (0.01 M) aqueous suspension of mancozeb. The dosed samples were analyzed for Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} by EDTA method. The results obtained are recorded in column 2 of Table 1.

In third set of experiment the powdered dried sample (0.5 g) was dosed with 1 ml of 0.2% aqueous suspension of mancozeb and after oxidizing it the final volume was made to 50 ml with distilled water. The concentration of Mn^{2+} was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

However, for the determination of Zn^{2+} , the above samples were diluted to 250 ml with distilled water. The results obtained are reported in column 3 of Table 1. These results show that the concentration of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} in plants determined by EDTA method is higher than that determined by atomic absorption. It may be due to the non-specific complexation of EDTA with Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} .

The values of standard deviation and the coefficient of variation are found to be 119.13–164.50 and 20.52–30.24 for Mn^{2+} and 137.17–197.72 and 20.06–28.84 for Zn^{2+} by EDTA method while 130.17 and 38.67 for Mn^{2+} and 59.46 and 45.16 for Zn^{2+} by atomic absorption spectro-photometer. Therefore, the EDTA method is a simple, inexpensive and readily available tool for determining the change in the heavy metal ion concentration in plants due to the use of metal containing fungicides such as mancozeb.

Experimental

Apparatus : Atomic absorption spectrophotometer (GBC902, Australia), pH meter (Elico, India) etc. were used. Disodium salt of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) or versenate (New Delhi) and mancozeb (75%) (Jaishri Agro Industries, Haryana) were used. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Versenate solution (0.1 M) was made in distilled water and eriochrome black T (0.5%) was made in ethanol. All other solutions were made as usual⁵.

The representative samples of different plants were collected during November–December, 2002 and January 2003 from a local market in Aligarh.

The plants were washed and cleaned with water and distilled water to remove surface contamination. The known quantity of the cleaned plants was spread uniformly on an

Note

Table I. Analysis of mancozeb residues in edible plants

Sample	EDTA method								Atomic absorption spectrophotometry			
	1. Sprayed samples				2. Dosed samples				Dosed samples			
	Expt. $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$		Calcd. $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$		Expt. $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$		Calcd. $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$		Expt. $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$		Calcd. $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$	
	Mn ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Zn ²⁺
Meithi	557	651	659	786	425	506	410	489	110	125	303	360
					849	1013	821	980				
Spinach	1030	1229	530	632	384	458	410	489	470	65	303	360
					848	1012	821	980				
Redish leaves	910	1157	307	366	970	1157	1234	1460	310	140	303	360
					242	289	410	489				
					505	603	821	980				
					729	868	1234	1460				
Sarson	1091	1289	616	735	1091	1301	1642	1959	440	240	303	360
					323	386	410	489				
Chukander leaves	1576	1880	564	672	747	892	821	980	300	125	303	360
					506	675	410	489				
					990	1881	821	980				
Chukander root	606	723	664	793	1454	1735	1234	1460	390	95	303	360
					485	578	410	489				
					869	1036	821	980				
					1454	1735	1234	1460				

asbestos sheet and then aqueous suspension of mancozeb was spread on the plants. The plants treated with mancozeb or untreated plants were dried at RT (25^o) and then at 100 ± 2^o in an electric oven till their weight was constant. The dried samples were mechanically grinded with pestle and mortar and passed through 1 mm sieve to reduce this material to a fine suitable for the analysis. Finally the samples were dried to constant weight and then preserved in airtight glass bottles or polythene bags.

The dried and powdered sample (0.5 g) was digested with concentrated nitric acid and then treated with nitric acid : perchloric acid (3 : 1) to obtain a colourless residue and the residue was dissolved in a small volume of 4 M HNO₃. The final volume was made up to 25 ml with distilled water. The dried powdered sample was dosed with aqueous suspension of mancozeb and then the above treatment was given to make the solution in distilled water. The solution so obtained was neutralized with ammonia solution and titrated with versenate using eriochrome black T indicator and ammonia buffer of pH 10 by following reported procedure⁵ for Mn²⁺ and Zn²⁺. The concentration of Mn²⁺ and Zn²⁺ was also determined in the above mentioned solutions by atomic absorption spectrophotometer after proper dilution.

The mancozeb solution or suspension was standardized by atomic absorption spectrophotometer by determining the concentrations of Mn²⁺ and Zn²⁺. Versenate solution was standardized with standard mancozeb solution that was used to analyze the plants material.

The following quantity of Mn²⁺ and Zn²⁺ was computed in mancozeb by taking molecular weight of mancozeb = 271.2, purity of mancozeb sample = 75%, atomic weight of manganese = 54.94 and atomic weight of zinc = 65.38. 1 ml of 10 mg mancozeb/500 ml solution contains 1.518 ppm of manganese and 1.808 ppm of zinc.

When the above-mentioned solution was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer the concentration of manganese and zinc was found to be 1.7 ppm and 1.9 ppm respectively.

The values of standard deviation (s) and coefficient of variation (CV) were calculated by using the expression given in Vogel's book⁵.

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